

Dioxotungsten(VI) complexes of α -nitroso- β -naphthol and β -nitroso- α -naphthol

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Abstract : Some novel dioxotungsten(VI) complexes of α -nitroso- β -naphthol and β -nitroso- α -naphthol having the compositions $[\text{WO}_2\text{L}_2\text{CIX}]$ (where X = Cl, NO₃, NCS or ClO₄ and L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol or β -nitroso- α -naphthol) have been synthesised and characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, IR, ¹H NMR and ESI mass spectral studies. The thermal behaviour of one of the complexes has also been examined. The ligands behave as neutral monodentate chelating agents in all the complexes, coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen only. The complexes are found to be monomeric and non-electrolytes with hexa-coordinate and tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry. The 3D molecular modeling and analysis for bond length and bond angles have also been carried out for complexes.

Keywords : Dioxotungsten(VI), α -nitroso- β -naphthol, β -nitroso- α -naphthol, thermal studies.

Introduction

High-valent oxotungsten complexes have attracted attention owing to their roles in various catalytic processes such as alcohol oxidation¹, olefin epoxidation² and olefin metathesis³. It is believed that most of these organic transformations and biological processes involve oxygen atom transfer (OAT) reactions as one of the crucial steps⁴. Numerous dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with a variety of supporting ligands have been prepared and studied⁵, whereas the chemistry of analogous dioxotungsten(VI) complexes is still inadequately studied^{6,7}. One reason for the relatively low number of known dioxotungsten(VI) complexes is the poor availability of suitable starting materials⁸, since typical synthetic routes start from soluble derivatives of WO₂Cl₂.

Metal complexes of α -nitroso- β -naphthol and β -nitroso- α -naphthol have received considerable attention because the ligands are capable of existing in quinone-oxime (I and III) and naphthol forms⁹ (II and IV), depending on the experimental conditions. In the metal complexes, the metal-ligand bond formation can occur in a variety of ways. There are conflicting reports in literature regarding the mode of attachment of these ligands to the metal.

Since these naphthols are versatile chelating agents, it was thought worthwhile exploring the possibility of isolating some dioxotungsten(VI) chelates of these ligands. We have synthesised and characterized eight new complexes having the composition $[\text{WO}_2(\text{ANBN})_2\text{CIX}]$ and $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{CIX}]$ (where ANBN = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, BNAN = β -nitroso- α -naphthol and X = Cl, NCS, NO₃ or ClO₄). The physico-chemical properties of these complexes are reported here.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are non-hygroscopic, deeply coloured solids and are remarkably stable in air. They are soluble in nitrobenzene, nitromethane, acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO, sparingly soluble in common organic

solvents such as methanol, ethanol and chloroform and insoluble in water.

Analytical data show that the complexes have the composition WO_2L_2ClX where $L = \alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol (ANBN) or β -nitroso- α -naphthol (BNAN) and $X = Cl, NCS, NO_3$ or ClO_4 . The molar conductance data (Table 1) indicate that all the complexes are non-electrolytes. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for systems with no unpaired electrons.

The important infrared spectral bands of the ligands and complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. There is a marked difference between the IR spectra of the pure ligands and that of the complexes. It is

also observed that some of the bands present in the spectra of pure ligands are absent in the spectra of the complexes. It has been suggested from IR spectral evidences that these ligands exist in the quinone-oxime form in the solid state¹⁰. In the IR spectrum of ANBN, a broad medium intensity band observed $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, has been attributed to the hydroxyl group. Also, in the spectra of its complexes, this band is observed, indicating that -OH group is still retained in the complexes and its non-participation in coordination. Two strong bands occurring at 1635 and 1521 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of ANBN can be assigned to the $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations respectively¹¹. A strong band at 1041 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the

Table 1. Analytical and molar conductance data of dioxotungsten(VI) complexes

Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Molar conductance		
	W	C	H	N	S	Cl	$C_6H_5NO_2$	CH_3CN	CH_3OH
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2Cl_2]$	28.76 (29.05)	38.42 (37.93)	2.01 (2.21)	4.59 (4.43)	-	11.09 (11.21)	4.1	32	26
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(NCS)Cl]$	28.95 (28.06)	38.98 (38.46)	2.54 (2.14)	6.52 (6.41)	4.68 (4.88)	5.92 (5.41)	5.8	45	35
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(NO_3)Cl]$	27.98 (27.89)	36.53 (36.40)	2.05 (2.12)	6.98 (6.37)	-	5.21 (5.38)	6.8	27	12
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(ClO_4)Cl]$	26.72 (26.39)	33.93 (34.45)	2.31 (2.01)	4.98 (4.02)	-	5.85 (5.09)	10.5	63	43
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2Cl_2]$	29.51 (29.06)	38.25 (37.93)	2.53 (2.21)	5.01 (4.43)	-	11.02 (11.21)	1.9	29	24
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(NCS)Cl]$	27.50 (28.06)	38.01 (38.46)	2.65 (2.14)	6.95 (6.41)	5.05 (4.88)	5.85 (5.41)	4.7	41	31
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(NO_3)Cl]$	27.97 (27.89)	35.53 (36.40)	2.23 (2.12)	6.52 (6.37)	-	5.81 (5.38)	3.8	23	15
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(ClO_4)Cl]$	27.05 (26.39)	35.45 (34.45)	2.55 (2.01)	4.75 (4.02)	-	5.76 (5.09)	11.3	59	45

Table 2. IR spectral data of ligands and complexes

Ligand and complex	$\nu(OH)$	$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu(N-O)$	$\nu_{sym}(O=W=O)$	$\nu_{asym}(O=W=O)$
ANBN	3454	1635	1521	1041	-	-
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2Cl_2]$	3435	1589	1522	1041	968	817
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(NCS)Cl]$	3414	1602	1521	1043	948	817
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(NO_3)Cl]$	3429	1600	1525	1045	972	817
$[WO_2(ANBN)_2(ClO_4)Cl]$	3435	1587	1525	1045	974	812
BNAN	3234	1666	1591	1066	-	-
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2Cl_2]$	3182	1624	1593	1066	974	815
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(NCS)Cl]$	3176	1635	1589	1065	974	813
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(NO_3)Cl]$	3089	1622	1593	1066	989	819
$[WO_2(BNAN)_2(ClO_4)Cl]$	3197	1625	1593	1066	975	846

stretching of N-O group¹². In the spectra of its complexes, the $\nu_{C=O}$ suffers a downward shift by about 30-50 cm^{-1} , while the $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{N-O} remain unaltered, indicating the coordination of $>C=O$ group only.

The infrared spectra of BNAN and its complexes show a broad band of medium intensity $\sim 3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, assignable to intramolecular hydrogen bonded -OH group. Strong bands at 1666, 1591 and 1066 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of BNAN are assigned to the $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{N-O} group respectively¹². In the spectra of its complexes, the $\nu_{C=O}$ suffers a downward shift by about 30-50 cm^{-1} , showing its involvement in complex formation. But the $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{N-O} remain unaltered, indicating its non-participation in complexation¹¹. Thus the IR spectral studies reveal that both the ligands act as neutral monodentate in all the complexes. This is confirmed by analytical data also.

Two strong bands observed in the vibrational spectra of all the complexes in the region $\sim 970 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $812-846 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{sym}} (O=W=O)$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}} (O=W=O)$ modes respectively. The IR data thus indicate the presence of a *cis*- WO_2 moiety^{13,14} in the com-

plexes as the *trans*- WO_2 structure would exhibit only $\nu_{\text{asym}} (O=W=O)$ mode while $\nu_{\text{sym}} (O=W=O)$ happens to be IR inactive. The WO_2^{2+} moiety prefers to form a *cis*-configuration due to the maximum utilization of the available $d\pi$ -orbitals of metal with the oxo groups.

The thiocyanate complexes of both the ligands, show very strong bands $\sim 2060 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{C-N}) along with medium intensity band $\sim 815 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{C-S}) and 490 cm^{-1} (δ_{N-C-S}) showing N-coordinated thiocyanate in these complexes¹⁵. The perchlorate complexes of ANBN and BNAN give strong bands at 1103, 1050, 630 cm^{-1} and 1150, 1093, 635 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the monodentate coordination of perchlorate group¹⁵. The IR spectra of nitrate complexes do not exhibit any band assignable to ionic nitrate. This is in conformity with the conductance data. The strong to medium intensity bands occurring around 1525, 1382, 1005 and 1521, 1402, 1010 cm^{-1} correspond to ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_2 frequencies of coordinated nitrate. The magnitude of splitting between ν_4 and ν_1 , clearly shows the monodentate nature of the nitrate group¹⁵.

Mass spectrum of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{ANBN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Mass spectrum of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

The ESI mass spectra of the complexes were compared and their stoichiometric compositions were confirmed. The complexes show the molecular ion peak at 633 m/z , which confirms the stoichiometry of the complexes as $\text{WO}_2\text{L}_2\text{Cl}_2$.

The thermal decomposition behaviour of the complex

$[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was studied using TG and DTG techniques by heating in air at a rate of 10 °C per min. The complex decomposes in two stages (Fig. 1), indicated by DTG peaks at 157 and 214 °C. There is no plateau between the two stages of decomposition and hence the intermediate cannot be isolated. Beyond 500 °C, the com-

Fig. 1. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

plex gradually decomposes to the final product¹⁶ WO_3 .

The kinetic evaluation of the thermal decomposition of the complex was carried out. All stages were selected for the study of the kinetics of decomposition of the complex. The kinetic parameters were calculated using Coats-Redfern equation. The value of $\log g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T \times 10^3$ plots gave straight line (Fig. 2), where slope and intercept were used for calculating the kinetic parameters by least square method. The fitness was tested by evalu-

Fig. 2. Coats-Redfern plot of stage 1(a) and stage 2(b) of decomposition of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

ating the correlation coefficient (Table 3). The entropy of activation (ΔS) was also calculated (Table 4).

The molecular modeling of the proposed configura-

tions were constructed using Modeling and Analysis software¹⁷ CHEM 3D Proversion 7.0.0. The possible 3D structures of the complexes, were optimized by molecular mechanics calculations, MM₂ giving the lowest energy CHEM 3D models. Fig. 3 shows the CHEM 3D model of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{ANBN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ while Fig. 4 shows that of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. The actual bond length and bond angles are given in Tables 5 and 6. They were calculated as a result of energy minimization in CHEM 3D, while the optimal bond length and optimal bond angle values are the most desirable/favourable (standard) bond length and bond angles established by the builder unit of the CHEM 3D. In most cases, the actual bond length and bond angles are close to the optimal values, and thus the proposed structures of the compounds as well as the others are acceptable.

On the basis of the above physico-chemical studies a hexa-coordinate and tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry is tentatively suggested for dioxotungsten complexes of ANBN and BNAN.

Experimental

WCl_6 (Acros Organics, Belgium), α -nitroso- β -naphthol and β -nitroso- α -naphthol (BDH, AR grade) were used as such. All other chemicals were of AR grade.

Metal, chloride and perchlorate were estimated by standard methods¹⁸. Elemental analyses were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre (STIC), Kochi. The IR spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. Molar conductances of the complexes in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol were measured at room temperature using an Elico direct reading conductivity meter at a concentration of $\sim 10^{-3}\text{ M}$. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature by Gouy method. ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a 300 MHz FT NMR instrument using TMS as reference. Thermal analysis of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ were carried out on a Mettler TG-50 thermobalance.

Preparation of the complexes :

The chloride complexes were prepared by adding methanolic solution of WCl_6 (2 mmol) dropwise with stirring to a methanolic solution of the ligand (4 mmol). The

Table 3. Computational details for the stages 1 and 2 decomposition of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Temp.	mg	TK	RT	WL	α	g_α	CR
Stage 1 ($n = 2, r = 0.99798$)							
120	6.14	393	2.54453	0	0	0	-
130	6.12	403	2.48139	0.02	0.05405	0.05714	-14.86007
140	6.1	413	2.42131	0.04	0.10811	0.12121	-14.15711
150	6.06	423	2.36407	0.08	0.21622	0.27586	-13.3826
160	6	433	2.30947	0.14	0.37838	0.6087	-12.63791
170	5.94	443	2.25734	0.2	0.54054	1.17647	-12.02462
180	5.9	453	2.20751	0.24	0.64865	1.84615	-11.61868
190	5.86	463	2.15983	0.28	0.75676	3.11111	-11.14047
200	5.82	473	2.11416	0.32	0.86486	6.4	-10.46189
Stage 2 ($n = 1.2, r = 0.99778$)							
160	6	433	2.30947	0	0	0	-
170	5.94	443	2.25734	0.06	0.15385	0.16988	-13.95983
180	5.9	453	2.20751	0.1	0.25641	0.30522	-13.41851
190	5.86	463	2.15983	0.14	0.35897	0.46506	-13.04104
200	5.81	473	2.11416	0.19	0.48718	0.71448	-12.65439
210	5.77	483	2.07039	0.23	0.58974	0.97529	-12.38505
220	5.72	493	2.0284	0.28	0.71795	1.44027	-12.03618
230	5.68	503	1.98807	0.32	0.82051	2.04958	-11.72354
240	5.64	513	1.94932	0.36	0.92308	3.35139	-11.27118

$$\text{CR} = \ln \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2}, \text{RT} = \frac{1 \times 10^3}{\text{TK}}$$

Table 4. Kinetic parameters for the thermal decomposition of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Stage	Peak temp. (°C)	Mass loss (%)	Activation energy (E) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Pre-exponential term (A) (s ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation (ΔS) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
I	157	7.51	98	3.70×10^6	-122.24
II	214	4.55	68.89	169.73	-206.34

Fig. 3. 3D Molecular structure of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{ANBN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

Fig. 4. 3D Molecular structure of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

Proposed 2D structure of $[\text{WO}_2(\text{ANBN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Proposed 2D structure of [WO₂(BNAN)₂Cl₂]

resulting solution was heated for ~5–10 min. On cooling the solution, the solid complex got separated, which was suction filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

The thiocyanate, nitrate and perchlorate complexes were prepared by the following general method. A methanolic solution of WCl₆ (2 mmol) containing ~0.5 g NH₄NCS or ~0.5 g LiNO₃ or 3–4 drops of perchloric acid, as the case may be, was added dropwise with stirring to a methanolic solution of the ligand (4 mmol). The resulting solution was heated for ~10 min at 60 °C. On

Table 5. Various bond lengths (*d*) and bond angles (γ) of the complex [WO₂(ANBN)₂Cl₂]

Bond	<i>d</i> _{actual} (Å)	<i>d</i> _{optimal} (Å)	Bond	<i>d</i> _{actual} (Å)	<i>d</i> _{optimal} (Å)
O(31)-H(45)	0.9396	0.9420	C(18)-C(21)	1.5027	1.4200
O(29)-H(44)	0.9428	0.9420	C(20)-C(15)	1.5217	1.5170
C(24)-H(43)	1.1034	1.1000	C(19)-C(20)	1.4011	1.5030
C(23)-H(42)	1.1032	1.1000	C(18)-C(19)	1.5015	1.4200
C(22)-H(41)	1.1035	1.1000	C(17)-C(18)	1.3749	1.5030
C(21)-H(40)	1.1024	1.1000	C(16)-C(17)	1.5087	1.3370
C(17)-H(39)	1.1013	1.1000	C(15)-C(16)	1.5236	1.5170
C(16)-H(38)	1.1075	1.1000	O(14)-C(15)	1.3277	1.2080
C(8)-H(37)	1.1031	1.1000	W(12)-O(13)	1.6815	
C(7)-H(36)	1.1027	1.1000	C(9)-O(11)	1.2289	1.2080
C(6)-H(35)	1.0971	1.1000	C(10)-N(30)	1.2817	1.2600
C(3)-H(34)	1.1023	1.1000	C(10)-C(5)	1.4769	1.5030
C(2)-H(33)	1.1018	1.1000	C(9)-C(10)	1.5053	1.5170
C(1)-H(32)	1.1026	1.1000	C(8)-C(9)	1.4785	1.5170
W(12)-Cl(27)	2.2969		C(7)-C(8)	1.3480	1.3370
W(12)-O(26)	1.6792		C(4)-C(7)	1.4607	1.5030
O(14)-W(12)	1.9489		C(6)-C(1)	1.3941	1.4200
O(11)-W(12)	1.9469		C(5)-C(6)	1.4079	1.4200
C(20)-N(28)	1.4767	1.2600	C(4)-C(5)	1.4103	1.4200
W(12)-Cl(25)	2.2981		C(3)-C(4)	1.4056	1.4200
C(24)-C(19)	1.5069	1.4200	C(2)-C(3)	1.3911	1.4200
C(23)-C(24)	1.5101	1.4200	C(1)-C(2)	1.3959	1.4200
C(22)-C(23)	1.5115	1.4200	N(30)-O(31)	1.3148	
C(21)-C(22)	1.5078	1.4200	N(28)-O(29)	1.3174	
Angle	γ _{actual} (deg.)	γ _{optimal} (deg.)	Angle	γ _{actual} (deg.)	γ _{optimal} (deg.)
H(45)-O(31)-N(30)	108.8257		C(21)-C(18)-C(17)	120.6319	120.0000
C(10)-N(30)-O(31)	127.7200		C(19)-C(18)-C(17)	120.6261	120.0000
H(44)-O(29)-N(28)	109.9042		H(39)-C(17)-C(18)	120.9206	120.0000
C(20)-N(28)-O(29)	117.3561		H(39)-C(17)-C(16)	119.9608	120.0000
H(43)-C(24)-C(19)	117.2995	120.0000	C(18)-C(17)-C(16)	118.3168	
H(43)-C(24)-C(23)	115.9441	120.0000	H(38)-C(16)-C(17)	113.4214	120.0000

Table-5 (contd.)

C(19)-C(24)-C(23)	119.3729		H(38)-C(16)-C(15)	113.0107	120.0000
H(42)-C(23)-C(24)	115.6506	120.0000	C(17)-C(16)-C(15)	109.3737	
H(42)-C(23)-C(22)	116.6318	120.0000	C(20)-C(15)-C(16)	110.2549	115.0000
C(24)-C(23)-C(22)	119.6217		C(20)-C(15)-O(14)	113.4411	123.0000
H(41)-C(22)-C(23)	116.3617	120.0000	C(16)-C(15)-O(14)	120.3089	123.0000
H(41)-C(22)-C(21)	115.0822	120.0000	W(12)-O(14)-C(15)	170.3610	
C(23)-C(22)-C(21)	118.5872		Cl(27)-W(12)-O(26)	169.5003	
H(40)-C(21)-C(22)	118.1013	120.0000	Cl(27)-W(12)-O(14)	85.8801	
H(40)-C(21)-C(18)	117.8966	120.0000	Cl(27)-W(12)-O(11)	88.0544	
C(22)-C(21)-C(18)	119.3886		Cl(27)-W(12)-Cl(25)	93.8307	
N(28)-C(20)-C(15)	120.0773	120.0000	Cl(27)-W(12)-O(13)	91.7311	
N(28)-C(20)-C(19)	124.1224	120.0000	O(26)-W(12)-O(14)	87.0693	
C(15)-C(20)-C(19)	114.3928	117.6000	O(26)-W(12)-O(11)	86.2898	
C(24)-C(19)-C(20)	121.2573	120.0000	O(26)-W(12)-Cl(25)	94.3029	
C(24)-C(19)-C(18)	119.3633	120.0000	O(26)-W(12)-O(13)	95.2313	
C(20)-C(19)-C(18)	118.8086	120.0000	O(14)-W(12)-O(11)	105.1550	
C(21)-C(18)-C(19)	118.5388	120.0000	O(14)-W(12)-Cl(25)	171.3712	
O(14)-W(12)-O(13)	83.7852				
O(11)-W(12)-Cl(25)	83.4450		C(1)-C(6)-C(5)	122.0698	
O(11)-W(12)-O(13)	171.0119		C(10)-C(5)-C(6)	123.7826	120.0000
Cl(25)-W(12)-O(13)	87.6050		C(10)-C(5)-C(4)	119.2820	120.0000
W(12)-O(11)-C(9)	179.2815		C(6)-C(5)-C(4)	116.9336	120.0000
N(30)-C(10)-C(5)	127.6799	120.0000	C(7)-C(4)-C(5)	121.1695	120.0000
N(30)-C(10)-C(9)	113.6338	120.0000	C(7)-C(4)-C(3)	117.8415	120.0000
C(5)-C(10)-C(9)	118.6743	117.6000	C(5)-C(4)-C(3)	120.9889	120.0000
O(11)-C(9)-C(10)	123.0737	123.0000	H(34)-C(3)-C(4)	120.5555	120.0000
O(11)-C(9)-C(8)	119.3133	123.0000	H(34)-C(3)-C(2)	118.6810	120.0000
C(10)-C(9)-C(8)	117.5261	115.0000	C(4)-C(3)-C(2)	120.7634	
H(37)-C(8)-C(9)	118.9425	120.0000	H(33)-C(2)-C(3)	120.5307	120.0000
H(37)-C(8)-C(7)	119.3388	120.0000	H(33)-C(2)-C(1)	120.4129	120.0000
C(9)-C(8)-C(7)	121.7091		C(3)-C(2)-C(1)	119.0559	
H(36)-C(7)-C(8)	118.4796	120.0000	H(32)-C(1)-C(6)	120.1804	120.0000
H(36)-C(7)-C(4)	119.9274	120.0000	H(32)-C(1)-C(2)	119.6446	120.0000
C(8)-C(7)-C(4)	121.5899		C(6)-C(1)-C(2)	120.1745	
H(35)-C(6)-C(1)	115.6352	120.0000			
H(35)-C(6)-C(5)	122.2944	120.0000			

Table 6. Various bond lengths (d) and bond angles (γ) of the complex $[\text{WO}_2(\text{BNAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

Bond	d_{actual} (Å)	d_{optimal} (Å)	Bond	d_{actual} (Å)	d_{optimal} (Å)
O(31)-H(45)	0.9402	0.9420	C(18)-C(19)	1.5063	1.4200
O(29)-H(44)	0.9454	0.9420	C(15)-C(18)	1.5104	1.4200
C(21)-H(43)	1.1020	1.1000	C(17)-C(12)	1.4973	1.3370
C(20)-H(42)	1.1015	1.1000	C(16)-C(17)	1.3712	1.5030
C(19)-H(41)	1.1007	1.1000	C(15)-C(16)	1.5002	1.4200
C(18)-H(40)	1.1016	1.1000	C(14)-C(15)	1.4276	1.5170

Table-6 (contd.)

C(17)-H(39)	1.1019	1.1000	C(13)-C(14)	1.5238	1.5170
C(12)-H(38)	1.1022	1.1000	C(12)-C(13)	1.5036	1.5030
C(10)-H(37)	1.1032	1.1000	C(8)-N(30)	1.2793	1.2600
C(9)-H(36)	1.1026	1.1000	C(7)-O(11)	1.2310	1.2080
C(5)-H(35)	1.0993	1.1000	C(10)-C(1)	1.4605	1.5030
C(4)-H(34)	1.1023	1.1000	C(9)-C(10)	1.3510	1.3370
C(3)-H(33)	1.1021	1.1000	C(8)-C(9)	1.4651	1.5030
C(2)-H(32)	1.1023	1.1000	C(7)-C(8)	1.5012	1.5170
W(23)-O(25)	1.6800		C(6)-C(7)	1.4891	1.5170
W(23)-O(24)	1.6812		C(6)-C(1)	1.4056	1.4200
W(23)-Cl(27)	2.2985		C(5)-C(6)	1.4037	1.4200
W(23)-Cl(26)	2.2957		C(4)-C(5)	1.3941	1.4200
O(22)-W(23)	1.9523		C(3)-C(4)	1.3976	1.4200
O(11)-W(23)	1.9493		C(2)-C(3)	1.3937	1.4200
C(14)-O(22)	1.3230	1.2080	C(1)-C(2)	1.4050	1.4200
C(13)-N(28)	1.5125	1.2600	N(30)-O(31)	1.3164	
C(21)-C(16)	1.5083	1.4200	N(28)-O(29)	1.3169	
C(20)-C(21)	1.5061	1.4200			
C(19)-C(20)	1.5042	1.4200			
Angle	γ_{actual} (deg.)	γ_{optimal} (deg.)	Angle	γ_{actual} (deg.)	γ_{optimal} (deg.)
H(45)-O(31)-N(30)	109.1667		O(25)-W(23)-O(22)	82.6972	
O(31)-N(30)-C(8)	123.6973		O(25)-W(23)-O(11)	165.7373	
H(44)-O(29)-N(28)	110.1271		O(24)-W(23)-O(22)	80.7231	
O(29)-N(28)-C(13)	117.5858		O(24)-W(23)-O(11)	83.6426	
Cl(27)-W(23)-Cl(26)	102.1528		O(22)-W(23)-O(11)	111.4018	
Cl(27)-W(23)-O(25)	83.7501		W(23)-O(22)-C(14)	175.8209	
Cl(27)-W(23)-O(24)	93.1566		H(43)-C(21)-C(20)	117.8863	120.0000
Cl(27)-W(23)-O(22)	163.7031		H(43)-C(21)-C(16)	119.4302	120.0000
Cl(27)-W(23)-O(11)	82.6449		C(20)-C(21)-C(16)	119.5788	
Cl(26)-W(23)-O(25)	93.1615		H(42)-C(20)-C(21)	119.1316	120.0000
Cl(26)-W(23)-O(24)	159.9522		H(42)-C(20)-C(19)	118.6235	120.0000
Cl(26)-W(23)-O(22)	87.6104		C(21)-C(20)-C(19)	116.7125	
Cl(26)-W(23)-O(11)	85.5473		H(41)-C(19)-C(20)	119.8227	120.0000
O(25)-W(23)-O(24)	101.3888		H(41)-C(19)-C(18)	119.7612	120.0000
C(20)-C(19)-C(18)	116.3994		H(36)-C(9)-C(8)	120.1967	120.0000
H(40)-C(18)-C(19)	115.0936	120.0000	C(9)-C(10)-C(1)	121.1133	
H(40)-C(18)-C(15)	117.6888	120.0000	H(36)-C(9)-C(10)	118.3658	120.0000
C(19)-C(18)-C(15)	118.1494		C(10)-C(9)-C(8)	121.4372	
H(39)-C(17)-C(16)	120.4299	120.0000	N(30)-C(8)-C(9)	122.7397	120.0000
H(39)-C(17)-C(12)	118.8897	120.0000	N(30)-C(8)-C(7)	118.6345	120.0000
C(16)-C(17)-C(12)	120.4908		C(9)-C(8)-C(7)	118.6182	117.6000
C(21)-C(16)-C(17)	118.8879	120.0000	O(11)-C(7)-C(8)	120.6739	123.0000
C(21)-C(16)-C(15)	119.3372	120.0000	O(11)-C(7)-C(6)	122.9662	123.0000
C(17)-C(16)-C(15)	121.6586	120.0000	C(8)-C(7)-C(6)	116.0843	115.0000
C(18)-C(15)-C(16)	118.5983	120.0000	C(7)-C(6)-C(5)	120.7010	117.6000

C(18)-C(15)-C(14)	119.2816	117.6000	C(7)-C(6)-C(1)	119.9927	117.6000
C(16)-C(15)-C(14)	122.0849	117.6000	C(5)-C(6)-C(1)	119.2758	120.0000
O(22)-C(14)-C(15)	123.3176	123.0000	H(35)-C(5)-C(6)	121.2773	120.0000
O(22)-C(14)-C(13)	119.7604	123.0000	H(35)-C(5)-C(4)	118.0569	120.0000
C(15)-C(14)-C(13)	116.8719	115.0000	C(6)-C(5)-C(4)	120.6608	
N(28)-C(13)-C(14)	120.8548	120.0000	H(33)-C(3)-C(4)	119.9674	120.0000
N(28)-C(13)-C(12)	118.9999	120.0000	H(33)-C(3)-C(2)	120.2505	120.0000
C(14)-C(13)-C(12)	119.6444	117.6000	C(4)-C(3)-C(2)	119.7622	
H(38)-C(12)-C(17)	118.2494	120.0000	H(32)-C(2)-C(3)	118.9663	120.0000
H(38)-C(12)-C(13)	117.9349	120.0000	H(32)-C(2)-C(1)	120.3896	120.0000
C(17)-C(12)-C(13)	118.4328		C(3)-C(2)-C(1)	120.6406	
W(23)-O(11)-C(7)	179.1445		C(10)-C(1)-C(6)	120.7103	120.0000
H(37)-C(10)-C(9)	119.0809	120.0000	C(10)-C(1)-C(2)	119.7915	120.0000
H(37)-C(10)-C(1)	119.6647	120.0000	C(6)-C(1)-C(2)	119.4982	120.0000

cooling the solution, black solid complex got separated, which was suction filtered, washed several times with aqueous methanol and dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*.

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